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Research Article

**THE IMPACT OF SMALL INTESTINAL BACTERIAL
OVERGROWTH ON THE GROWTH OF CHILDREN AND
ADOLESCENTS.**¹Dr Qurat-ul-ain, ²Dr Adeel Ahmad, ³Dr Ujala Khalid,¹MBBS, Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur.²MBBS, Shalamar Medical and Dental College, Lahore.³MBBS, Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore.**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

The clinical sign and symptoms of SIBO are loss of appetite, abdominal pain, nausea, bloating, and an uncomfortable feeling of fullness after eating, diarrhea, Unintentional weight loss and malnutrition. The common causes of SIBO are decreased intestinal mobility or any chronic disease such as diabetes. Irritable bowel syndrome, functional abdominal pain, and functional constipation are also found in functional gastrointestinal disorders. Poverty and nutrient malabsorption are associated with SIBO as a part of environmental enteropathy. In underdeveloped countries, when interpreting the concentrations of hydrogen (H₂) and methane (CH₄) in the lactulose breath test height impairment has been seen in children with SIBO. While using H₂ in other studies to interpret the test the conclusion was contrary, it does not show any association of height deficit in children with asymptomatic SIBO. It could be the justification for SIBO treatment regardless of symptoms.

Total 140 patients age ranges from six months to 19 years were enrolled into the study. The statistical study did not show higher positivity, with a statistically significant difference in SIBO in any of the diseases that motivated the request for the H₂ breath test.

The current study has concluded that the production of H₂ and CH₄ increased in children during the colonic period of the breath test. And the patients with SIBO associated with gastrointestinal tract diseases have lower height values and those under ten years also have lower weight values when compared to patients without SIBO.

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INTRODUCTION:

A diversified syndrome which is characterized by the presence of abnormal increase in the total aggregate of bacteria that normally grows in other part of gut starts growing in the small intestine is known as small intestinal bacterial over growth syndrome. The clinical sign and symptoms of SIBO are loss of appetite, abdominal pain, nausea, bloating, and an uncomfortable feeling of fullness after eating, diarrhea, Unintentional weight loss and malnutrition. The common causes of SIBO are decreased intestinal mobility or any chronic disease such as diabetes. Irritable bowel syndrome, functional abdominal pain, and functional constipation are also found in functional gastrointestinal disorders. Poverty and nutrient malabsorption are associated with SIBO as a part of environmental enteropathy. In underdeveloped countries, when interpreting the concentrations of hydrogen (H₂) and methane (CH₄) in the lactulose breath test height impairment has seen in children with SIBO. While using H₂ in other studies to interpret the test the conclusion was contrary, it does not show any association of height deficit in children with asymptomatic SIBO. It could be the justification for SIBO treatment regardless of symptoms. The analysis of microbiota in jejunal content is considered the gold standard for SIBO diagnosis yet a difficult and invasive method which is difficult to perform and also expensive. An alternative for the diagnosis of SIBO is the respiratory test after ingestion of lactulose or glucose. It analyzes the concentration of breath samples which contains H₂ and CH₄ in breath samples. An increase anaerobic fermentation is present in the large intestine caused by the production of H₂ and CH₄. More proximal portions of the gastrointestinal tract have the production with the presence of SIBO. The aim of the study is to evaluate the association of SIBO and weight and height impairment in children and adolescents with digestive tract diseases.

METHOD:

It was an observational cross-sectional study. Patients who underwent lactulose breathe test under age 19 were recruited into the study. Demographic data was obtained along with gender, date of birth, date of first visit, weight and height at first visit, diagnostic hypothesis, test date, weight and height with a maximum interval of two months before or after the breath test. The test was executed in the morning after fasting for six to eight hours. Initially, oral hygiene with 0.5% chlorhexidine was performed. Then, the fasting expired air sample was collected. In the next step, a diluted solution of containing 10 gram of lactose and 100 mL water was administered orally. Results were expressed in parts per million (ppm). SIBO was defined as the concentration of H₂ more than

20 ppm and CH₄ more than 10 ppm in relation to the fasting value until the sample collected at 60 minutes after lactulose ingestion. Non-H₂ producers were considered as those patients who did not present a minimum elevation of 10 ppm H₂ in exhaled air after lactulose ingestion in any of the samples. To analyze the categorical variables chi-square was used. Mann-Whitney test or Student's t-test was used to evaluate the numerical variables depending on the distribution of each variable.

RESULTS:

Total 140 patients age ranges from six months to 19 years were enrolled into the study. The statistical study did not show higher positivity, with a statistically significant difference in SIBO in any of the diseases that motivated the request for the H₂ breath test.

Participants were classified into two groups; with SIBO and without SIBO. Among 140 patients, 70 participants were classified into nonH₂ producers. Among these 20 non-H₂ -producing patients, four were diagnosed with SIBO based on increased exhaled air CH₄ concentration after lactulose ingestion. There was statistically difference in the height-age Z score of children who were having low SIBO than those children without SIBO. While comparing age Z score with BMI there was no difference detected between both the groups with SIBO and without SIBO. According to the presence of bacterial overgrowth in the small intestine weight-age-z-score was obtained of patients under ten years. Weight-age Z-scores were lower in SIBO patients. In the area under the concentration curve of H₂ and CH₄ obtained in the breath test, used as lactulose fermentation indicators. The production of H₂ and CH₄ was higher in patients with SIBO in the period between zero and 60 minutes and between 60 and 180 minutes.

DISCUSSION:

The current study demonstrates that children having digestive tract disease diagnosed with SIBO have less significance with weight and height as compared to those who were not having SIBO. It has also indicated that breath tests of patients with SIBO have shown higher production of H₂ and CH₄ in exhaled air it was not only present in the small intestine but also in the colonic phase of the breath test.

SIBO was most often found to be associated with other digestive tract diseases such as cow's-milk protein allergy, constipation, chronic diarrhea, gastroesophageal reflux disease, and lactose intolerance. Previous studies have demonstrated that children with SIBO associated with unfavorable environmental conditions, who may

have environmental enteropathy or minimal enteric dysfunction. Environment changes would bring betterment in the health. The ideal would be to change of environmental conditions to a situation with good health conditions. A study conducted by São Paulo Metropolitan Region has performed antimicrobial treatment on children from community. The presence of weight and height deficit, as observed in the present study, could be an additional justification for the treatment of asymptomatic SIBO with antibiotic therapy. The therapeutic effectiveness of metronidazole with combination of sulfamethoxazole-trimethoprim for 2 weeks in the treatment of SOBI has linked with unfavorable conditions. Literature has shuffled the therapeutic options with other antibiotics such as rifaximin, a study carried out in 2011 has shown that 20% treated participants who were suffering from chronic pain and SIBO has normal breath test. There was no statistically difference in symptom improvement. Similarly another study conducted with placebo effect it concluded that there was no difference in symptom improvement between the placebo group and the rifaximin group. Considering that there is an abnormality in the small intestine microbiota in SIBO, some authors include SIBO in the broad concept of dysbiosis and thus suggest the use of probiotics. While there is no evidence present currently with the use of probiotics in the treatment or prevention of SIBO. The current study has given the statistics of association of SIBO with weight height might be observed as further reasons for performing SIBO drug treatment. The statistics of individual z-score are remarkable of the current study; values of patients with and without SIBO were used to indicate the nutritional repercussions of SIBO on anthropometric data. In the comparison group, sensitive measures were used. In 2009, European committee has recommended that glucose should be preferable substrate for the diagnosis of SOBI in the breath test. But in many studies lactulose has always been used for SIBO research using the breath test. In a study, lactulose and glucose both were used and showed that h₂ production with glucose was very low which was supposed to be the reason of underestimated prevalence of SIBO in the study population.

It was recommended to use both lactulose and glucose as a substrate to be used in a study on SIBO using the breath test for better results. In the exhaled breath test the use of CH₄ together with H₂ the sensitivity of the breath test increases for the diagnosis of SIBO.

This is suggestive that intestinal microbiota abnormalities in patients with SIBO are not restricted to the small intestine. Therefore, the elevation of H₂ and CH₄ in exhaled air for

diagnosis of SIBO should be restricted to the first 60 minutes of the breath test, considering that the orofecal transit time is shorter in children than in adults.

CONCLUSION:

The current study has concluded that the production of H₂ and CH₄ increased in children during the colonic period of the breath test. And the patients with SIBO associated with gastrointestinal tract diseases have lower height values and those under ten years also have lower weight values when compared to patients without SIBO.

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